

NETWORK CONFERENCE

Balancing priorities: An importance-performance analysis of cultural heritage conservation

BOOK OF ABSTRACTS

**Network Conference: Balancing Priorities: An Importance-Performance Analysis of
Cultural Heritage Conservation**

28 May 2026 - 29 May 2026, Targoviste, Romania

The conference is co-funded by the Erasmus+ project Knowledge & Creativity European University KreativEU (101177256 – ERASMUS-EDU-2024-EUR-UNIV), is hosted by Valahia University of Targoviste, Romania, in collaboration with the Polytechnic University of Tomar, Portugal, and Trnava University, Slovakia, and is also held under the aegis of the UNESCO UNITWIN Network: Heritage Preservation and Science Communication for Sustainable Communities.

<https://kreativeu.org/en/news/374/>

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SCHEDULE

Thursday, May 28th, 2026

8 ⁰⁰ – 10 ⁰⁰	Registration
10 ⁰⁰ – 10 ³⁰	Red Hall Opening Ceremony
Red Hall <i>Creative Conservation; New Technologies & Methods</i> Chairperson: Lucia Novakova & Sergiu Musteata	
10 ³⁰ – 10 ⁵⁰	<i>Adrián Kobetič</i> - Notes on Dialogues Between Contemporary Art and Ruins
10 ⁵⁰ – 11 ¹⁰	<i>Matěj Šindelář</i> – Integrating Photogrammetry, 3d Modeling, and the Latest AI Models for Heritage Preservation and Public Dissemination: Digital Twin of the Reliquary of St. Maurus as a Primary Case Study
11 ¹⁰ – 11 ³⁰	<i>Marius Lungescu, Maria-Catalina Ghinea</i> - Advanced Characterisation of Substrate Materials used in Mural Painting in the Secco Technique – Case Study: The Royal Railway Station of Curtea de Argeș
11 ³⁰ – 11 ⁵⁰	Coffee Break
Red Hall <i>New Technologies & Methods</i> Chairperson: Katarzyna Łukaniszyn-Domaszewska & Silviu Miloiu	
11 ⁵⁰ – 12 ¹⁰	<i>Graziella Roselli</i> - The "Skin of Time": Memory, Beauty and Safety of Historic Buildings (Diagnostics and Restoration)
12 ¹⁰ – 12 ³⁰	<i>Elena Badea, Cristina Carsote, Marianne Odlyha</i> - Unravelling Collagen Mysteries: How Thermal Analysis and Multi-Technique Synergy Advance the Characterization and Diagnosis of Leather, Skin, and Parchment
12 ³⁰ – 12 ⁵⁰	<i>Adina Boroneanț</i> - Archaeometric Investigations on Early Neolithic Pottery from SW Romania
12 ⁵⁰ – 14 ⁰⁰	Lunch

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Red Hall	
<i>Heritage between Past and Future</i>	
Chairpersons: Monica Mărgărit & Adrián Kobetič	
14 ⁰⁰ – 14 ²⁰	<i>Svitlana Linda</i> - Cultural Heritage at Risk: Preservation of Architecture in Conflict Zones
14 ²⁰ – 14 ⁴⁰	<i>Ruxandra Cristina Săpoi, Margareta Cheresteș, Denisa Valentina Negreanu, Alexandra Maria Nacu, Melissa Elena Țoi, Alina Bălan</i> - Ionizing Radiation Risk in Cultural Heritage Conservation Activities
14 ⁴⁰ – 15 ⁰⁰	<i>Justyna Kleszcz</i> - Evolution of Morphological Analysis of Wrocław Quarter Development in the Area of Former Sand Gate and its Impact on Modern Urban Structure
15 ⁰⁰ – 15 ²⁰	<i>Andrea Bernath</i> - Ethics and Expertise for the Benefit of Cultural Heritage
15 ²⁰ – 15 ⁴⁰	<i>Luís Filipe Raposo Pereira</i> - Conservation Ethics and Sacred Heritage: Reflections from a Megillat Esther
15 ⁴⁰ – 16 ⁰⁰	<i>Elitsa Lazarova</i> - Cultural Heritage in the Context of The Smart Shrinking Cities: Between Past and Future
16 ⁰⁰ – 16 ²⁰	Coffee Break
Red Hall	
<i>Heritage between Past and Future</i>	
Chairpersons: Justyna Kleszcz & Marcin Gałkowski	
16 ²⁰ – 16 ⁴⁰	<i>Lucia Nováková, Silviu Miloiu</i> – Heritage Futures in Eastern Europe: Rewilding and Selective Conservation in Post-Socialist Landscapes
16 ⁴⁰ – 17 ⁰⁰	<i>Beatrice Menghini</i> - The Role of Cultural Heritage in Post-Earthquake Resilience: The Church of San Francesco in Camerino
17 ⁰⁰ – 17 ²⁰	<i>Rana Habibi, Anelia Georgieva</i> - Between Loss and Continuity: Collective Memory and Heritage Landscapes in the Netherlands
17 ²⁰ – 17 ⁴⁰	<i>Maria- Catalina Ghinea</i> - The Icon Panel in Wallachia During the 18 th –19 th Centuries: Historical Context and Aspects Concerning the Morphology of Degradation, with Particular Emphasis on Light as a Deterioration Factor
17 ⁴⁰ – 18 ⁰⁰	<i>Ângela Sofia Alves Ferraz</i> - Rethinking Conservation Training through Ethnographic Collections
18 ⁰⁰ – 18 ²⁰	<i>Alexandru Popa</i> - Cost-Efficiency in Subsurface Heritage Management: An Importance-Performance Analysis of Magnetometry at the Reci-Comolău Civilian Settlement in SE Transylvania
19 ³⁰	Welcome Reception

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Friday, May 29th, 2026

8 ⁰⁰ – 9 ³⁰	Registration
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Red Hall

Heritage between Past and Future

Chairperson: Graziella Roselli & Gabriel Gorghiu

9 ³⁰ – 9 ⁵⁰	<i>Silviu Miloiu, Elena-Adriana Ciocoiu, Ioan Alexandru Vălu</i> – From Grave Goods to Gallery Narratives: Women’s Agency in the Christianisation of Sweden and Norway
9 ⁵⁰ – 10 ¹⁰	<i>Maria Catanheira Pereira De Moura Belo</i> – Characterization and Conservation of a Graphic Design Collection: Case Study Collection B2, Salette and José Brandão Design Studio
10 ¹⁰ – 10 ³⁰	<i>Ana Ilie, Andrei Scărlătescu, Tudor Hila, Bogdan Ciupercă</i> - New Museotechnical Methods Applied to a Cache of Metal Artefacts from the Archaeological Collection of the National Museum Complex “Curtea Domnească”, Târgoviște (Romania)
10 ³⁰ – 10 ⁵⁰	<i>Sergiu Musteata</i> - Rediscovering the Tatars' Medieval Heritage on the Territory of the Republic of Moldova

10 ⁵⁰ – 11 ¹⁰	Coffee Break
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Red Hall

Risk Assessment & Disaster Recovery; Heritage between Past and Future

Chairpersons: Svitlana Linda & Alexandru Popa

11 ¹⁰ – 11 ³⁰	<i>Bilge Aksay, Mücahit Ersoy, Armagan Gumus</i> - Leveraging Heritage Identity for Sustainable Business and AI-Driven Business Continuity as a strategy for natural disasters
11 ³⁰ – 11 ⁵⁰	<i>Zameer Hussain Jamali</i> - Biodegradable Plastics in Crop Production: Effects on Soil Environment and Agronomic Performance
12 ¹⁰ – 12 ³⁰	<i>Dumitrița Daniela Filip, Viorica Rusu-Bolindeț, Gheorghina Olariu</i> - Unveiling the Wall Painting Technique from the Governor’S Palace in Apulum. Preliminary Remarks
12 ³⁰ – 12 ⁵⁰	<i>Maria Stamate</i> - The Limits of Private Intervention in Public Heritage: A Managerial Critique of the Radu Varia Restoration Project on Brâncuși’s Endless Column (1996–2000)

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12 ⁵⁰ – 13 ¹⁰	<i>Claudia Stihi</i> - Bridging Past and Future: A Study of Nuclear Heritage in Romania
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13 ¹⁰ – 14 ⁰⁰	Lunch
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Red Hall

Socio-Economic Value & Other

Chairpersons: Rana Habibi & Mücahit Ersoy

14 ⁰⁰ – 14 ²⁰	<i>Katarzyna Łukaniszyn-Domaszewska, Katarzyna Mazur-Włodarczyk</i> – Craft-Oriented Educational Heritage
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14 ²⁰ – 14 ⁴⁰	<i>Katarzyna Łukaniszyn-Domaszewska, Katarzyna Mazur-Włodarczyk</i> – Cultural Heritage as A Resource for Mental Health and Well-Being
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14 ⁰⁰ – 15 ⁰⁰	<i>Alina Chiciudean</i> - Rethinking and Activating Heritage as a Socio-Economic Resource in Dragu, Romania
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15 ⁰⁰ – 15 ²⁰	<i>Raluca Romok</i> - Electrotipe of the Parade Shield "Cellini" from the Royal Collection of Peleş Castle
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15 ²⁰ – 15 ⁴⁰	<i>Marcin Gałkowski</i> - Heritage Public Spaces, Excluded Users: Accessibility of Small-Town Market Squares in Southern Poland
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15 ⁴⁰ – 16 ⁰⁰	<i>Laura Monica Gorghiu, Gabriel Gorghiu, Silviu Miloiiu</i> - From Students' Voice to Curriculum Design in Applied Sciences – Building an Eco-Cultural Heritage Master's Aligned with the Green and Digital Transitions
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16 ⁰⁰ – 16 ¹⁰	Coffee Break
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Red Hall

New Technologies & Methods

Chairpersons: Cristiana Radulescu & Alina Chiciudean

16 ¹⁰ – 16 ³⁰	<i>Toma-Andrei Bucuroiu</i> – "La Policiori" Rock Shelter as a Case Study for Modern Rock Art Recording Methods
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16 ³⁰ – 16 ⁵⁰	<i>Andreea Popa</i> - Making the Invisible Visible: Visualizing Magnetometry Data to Align Stakeholder Priorities in Heritage Conservation
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16 ⁵⁰ – 17 ¹⁰	<i>Adrian Irimia, Valentina Voinea, Monica Mărgărit</i> – Recreating Prehistoric Gestures: Experimental Archaeology and the Bone-Pointed Tools of The Hamangia Culture
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17 ¹⁰ – 17 ³⁰	<i>Raluca Toader, Monica Mărgărit</i> - From Shell to Ornament: Experimental Archaeology as a Tool for Reconstructing Prehistoric Adornment Practices at the Lower Danube
17 ³⁰ – 17 ⁵⁰	<i>Dragos-Viorel Brezoi, Anca-Irina Gheboianu, Adrian Iordache</i> - Oxide Phase Markers Identified in Decorative Materials from Hamangia Ceramics: A High-Resolution Analysis Method for Reconstructing Technological Firing Scenarios
17 ⁵⁰ – 18 ¹⁰	<i>Costel Constantin</i> - Ellipsometry, Transmission, And Photoluminescence Characterisation of Mn-Doped ITO Thin Films Deposited by DC Magnetron Sputtering
18 ¹⁰ – 19 ⁰⁰	Round Table – Scientific Report Defence Chairpersons: Silviu Miloiu, Costel Coroban, Lucia Nováková, and Renato de Leone Title: Runestones Commissioned by Women in Sweden
19 ⁰⁰ – 19 ¹⁰	Closing ceremony
20 ⁰⁰	Diner

Topic: Risk Assessment & Disaster Recovery

LEVERAGING HERITAGE IDENTITY FOR SUSTAINABLE BUSINESS AND AI-DRIVEN BUSINESS CONTINUITY AS A STRATEGY FOR NATURAL DISASTERS

BILGE AKSAY¹, MÜCAHİT ERSOY¹, ARMAGAN GUMUS¹

Abstract. Natural disasters such as extreme weather, fires, earthquakes, volcanic eruptions, and droughts are putting 59.25% of the 1,146 \$ cities with a population of at least half a million people at risk. According to the World Risk Report 2025, the losses are not due solely to disasters but also to other factors such as urbanization, perception, preparedness, and poverty. Under these risks, sustainable ecosystems lean on the triple bottom line as environmental, social, and economic, which forms a holistic framework. Thus, two research questions of this theoretical paper are “How many managers/owners use 'Heritage Identity' for sustainable business activities?” and “How can AI open venues for business continuity plans?”

Based on the first research question, the literature was evaluated by AI-backed programs. Corporate heritage identity, corporate social responsibility, sustainability-related identities, organizational identity, and digital cultural heritage came forward among the constructs in the studies, whereas social learning theory and corporate heritage stewardship, sustainability, and corporate sustainability are used as theoretical lenses. A limited amount of research denotes trait theory and learning theories among managers/owners for valuing cultural heritage as a business asset. In pursuit of creating sustainable and resilient social ecosystems, artificial intelligence may facilitate the continuity plans of enterprises. At the business level, the literature emphasizes AI as a tool for risk assessment, crisis management, supply chain analytics, and human resources empowerment. AI tools may also aid eco-system continuity by smart cities, multi-faceted real-time data analysis, via deep learning and geospatial tools for hyper-local and multi-scale risk assessment. Contrary to the lack of theoretical diversity among the papers related to heritage identity or sustainable business activities, resilience, decision making, and evaluation theories, such as cost-benefit, multi-criteria decision

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making, analytical hierarchy process, and learning theories, are imposed on business continuity plans. Based on the literature review, the authors concluded that AI is utilized and/or understood as a business asset where a literature and/or practice gap exists for business owners' and managers' AI capabilities. This research tries to open a discussion among different academic fields where unified but comprehensive approaches may aid disaster recovery and sustainability.

Keywords: Natural disasters; businesses; disaster management.

Conference Track: Risk Assessment & Disaster Recovery

LEISURE AND CULTURAL ACTIVITIES AS POST-DISASTER RECOVERY

ANDREW SHAW¹

Abstract. Disasters affecting heritage sites cause both the loss of material culture and the disruption of community cultural identity. While heritage conservation literature extensively addresses physical reconstruction, it often overlooks the social-cultural dimensions of recovery and the role of everyday leisure activities in regenerating both tangible and intangible heritage. This paper argues that leisure communities and cultural activities are essential to heritage disaster recovery. Drawing on Community-Based Disaster Risk Management (CBDRM) principles, it presents a framework for integrating cultural programming into heritage disaster recovery planning. Through comparative analysis of disaster-hit heritage contexts, the paper demonstrates how festivals, events, heritage tourism, and community-led activities serve multiple recovery functions: psychological healing, social network reconstruction, and cultural continuity. Communities with strong leisure-based connections to heritage sites demonstrate greater resilience and more sustainable approaches to adaptive stewardship. This research bridges disaster risk management, leisure studies, and heritage conservation, offering insights for heritage professionals and policy-makers as climate change increases threats to cultural heritage globally.

Keywords: Cultural heritage; disaster recovery; community participation; leisure communities; resilience; intangible heritage.

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Topic: Creative Conservation

NOTES ON DIALOGUES BETWEEN CONTEMPORARY ART AND RUINS

ADRIÁN KOBETIČ¹

Abstract. Arthur Danto, in connection with the definitions of contemporary art, says that it creates space for the past. Unlike modernism and postmodernism, contemporary art is interested in older art history, appropriating or reinterpreting many images from it, which, according to Danto, is one of its key features. Thanks to this, the ruin, as a sign of the past, often appears in the interests of contemporary art. This happens for various reasons, depending on the strategy the given work employs in its dialogue with the past. It is therefore a type of dialogical relationship that contemporary art decides to have with the past. This dialogue is two-sided, even though the ruins seem to have long been "dead". At the moment when contemporary art stands "face to face" with the past, it faces a different type of temporality. According to Didi-Huberman, when we stand before art, we stand before time. However, when we stand before a ruin, time also becomes a kind of existential value, linked to extinction, radically different from the anachronistic nature of art, which it disrupts. When contemporary art encounters a ruin, different temporalities thus intersect, creating a special "Here and Now", as Walter Benjamin spoke of it, which has become key for site-specific art. Contemporary art derives a new value from this relationship, which Boris Groys calls "time-based art". In this direction, several basic types of dialogue between contemporary art and the ruin have gradually become established, or rather, how contemporary art enters the environment of the ruin. My contribution will, using examples from Slovak art after 1989, seek to define the basic strategies of approaches, of which there will be three in particular: the ruin as a space for an exhibition, the construction of the ruin, and artistic intervention into the ruin. However, the main goal of the contribution will be to point out how contemporary art can serve in the presentation, popularization, and conservation of ruins.

Keywords: Contemporary art; ruins; time; exhibition; intervention.

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Topic: New Technologies & Methods

UNRAVELLING COLLAGEN MYSTERIES: HOW THERMAL ANALYSIS AND MULTI-TECHNIQUE SYNERGY ADVANCE THE CHARACTERISATION AND DIAGNOSIS OF LEATHER, SKIN, AND PARCHMENT

ELENA BADEA^{1,2}, CRISTINA CARSONTE³, MARIANNE ODLYHA⁴

Abstract. Collagen-based materials such as leather, parchment, and skin present significant analytical challenges due to their chemical and physical complexity, heterogeneity, and susceptibility to degradation. Traditional single-method approaches are often insufficient to characterize their composition, condition, and deterioration patterns accurately. This presentation explores how integrating thermal analysis techniques, including micro-Differential Scanning Calorimetry (micro-DSC), Thermal Microscopy (MHT method), Thermogravimetry (TGA), and Dynamic Mechanical Analysis (DMA), with complementary methods such as FTIR-ATR, Raman spectroscopy, NMR, and neutron radiography, provides a multidimensional view of collagen matrices at both molecular and bulk levels. By leveraging the strengths of each technique, researchers and conservators can overcome the limitations posed by overlapping analytical signals, local heterogeneity, and evolving degradation markers. Case studies highlight how combined approaches yield robust diagnostics for historical and archaeological collagen artefacts, inform risk assessment, and guide conservation strategies. This multi-technique and multi-scale approach not only enhances the reliability of damage ranking and material identification but also sets new benchmarks for the preservation and study of complex, aged biomaterials.

Keywords: Collagen-based materials; microcalorimetry; thermal analysis; multi-technique approach; damage assessment; preservation.

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Topic: New Technologies & Methods

OXIDE PHASE MARKERS IDENTIFIED IN DECORATIVE MATERIALS FROM HAMANGIA CERAMICS: A HIGH-RESOLUTION ANALYSIS METHOD FOR RECONSTRUCTING TECHNOLOGICAL FIRING SCENARIOS

DRAGOS-VIOREL BREZOI¹, ANCA-IRINA GHEBOIANU², ADRIAN IORDACHE¹

Abstract. This study proposes a refined methodology to determine the firing intervals and atmospheric conditions of Hamangia ceramics by analyzing the mineralogical transformations of decorative materials. Unlike traditional bulk ceramic analysis, this research focuses on the white paste inlays and red paints, where specific oxidic phase markers serve as internal "paleo-thermometers". By integrating data from high-resolution analysis methods like Wavelength Dispersive X-ray Fluorescence (WDXRF), X-ray Diffraction (XRD), Fourier-Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR), and Digital Optical Microscopy, key compounds were identified whose presence correlates with specific thermal stability thresholds. The identification of these phases allows for a precise deduction of firing temperatures and thermal regimes (oxidizing vs. reducing) practiced by Eneolithic potters. This micro-analytical approach to decorative layers provides a high-resolution perspective on the technological firing scenario of Hamangia culture pottery, providing a robust framework for characterizing cultural heritage through advanced analytical techniques.

Keywords: Hamangia; Eneolithic; decorative materials; firing markers.

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Topic: New Technologies & Methods

FROM SHELL TO ORNAMENT: EXPERIMENTAL ARCHAEOLOGY AS A TOOL FOR RECONSTRUCTING PREHISTORIC ADORNMENT PRACTICES AT THE LOWER DANUBE

RALUCA TOADER¹, MONICA MĂRGĂRIT¹

Abstract. Experimental archaeology has proven to be an invaluable methodological framework for understanding and reconstructing prehistoric technological behaviors, offering insights that purely analytical approaches cannot fully provide. The present study integrates archaeological evidence with experimental data in order to investigate the 'chaîne opératoire' involved in the production of gastropod shell adornments discovered in several prehistoric settlements along the Lower Danube. The archaeological record reveals a diverse assemblage of processed gastropod shells - encompassing both local and exotic species - most likely procured through inter-community exchange networks, reflecting the social and symbolic significance of personal adornments in prehistoric communities. The majority of these artifacts were perforated and incorporated into necklaces or bracelets, while a smaller number were used as appliqués sewn onto garments. To quantify the investment of time and effort embedded in the manufacturing process, a systematic experimental program was developed, meticulously documenting all relevant variables: raw material acquisition, successive technological stages, duration of each operation, tools employed, and the progressive development of use-wear traces. The experimentally produced items were subsequently assembled into complete adornments, enabling the monitoring of surface use-wear and perforation evolution over time. This experimental approach not only contributes to a more accurate reconstruction of prehistoric craft practices but also enhances the valorization of the archaeological heritage of the Lower Danube area, offering new perspectives on the social, economic, and symbolic dimensions of prehistoric ornamental traditions.

Keywords: Experimental archaeology; prehistoric technological behaviors; gastropod shell adornments; lower Danube; symbolic dimension.

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Topic: New Technologies & Methods

RECREATING PREHISTORIC GESTURES: EXPERIMENTAL ARCHAEOLOGY AND THE BONE POINTED TOOLS OF THE HAMANGIA CULTURE

ADRIAN IRIMIA¹, VALENTINA VOINEA¹, MONICA MĂRGĂRIT¹

Abstract. Archaeological heritage is not merely a collection of silent objects - it embodies the knowledge, skills, and worldviews of past communities. Yet transforming fragmentary material evidence into meaningful, accessible knowledge requires methodological bridges between the archaeological record and the living public. This paper argues that experimental archaeology constitutes one of the most powerful such bridges, and illustrates this potential through a case study focused on the pointed bone tools of the Hamangia culture (Chalcolithic, end of the 6th – beginning of the 5th millennium BC), recovered from the settlement of Cheia-Vatra Satului, in the Dobrogea region of south-eastern Romania. The bone tools under analysis were produced from caprine long bones using a technically demanding method - quadri-partition by double grooving - a technique with deep prehistoric roots, attested from the Upper Palaeolithic to the Neolithic across the Near East and Europe. The particular skill this method requires, and the cultural significance it carries, make it an especially compelling subject for heritage valorization. Our experimental programme reconstructed the full chaîne opératoire - from the selection and preparation of raw bone to the production of finished pointed implements - documenting each manufacturing gesture, the time invested, and the tools employed. The replicas were subsequently used in a range of functional tests (hide perforation, wood processing, shell and bone perforation, vegetable fiber production), and submitted to systematic use-wear analysis examining polish, striations, microfractures, and micro-topography. Beyond its strictly scientific contribution - reconstructing the manufacture and function of these Chalcolithic implements - this approach demonstrates how experimental replication can render intangible prehistoric knowledge tangible and communicable. By recreating ancient gestures and skills,

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experimental archaeology offers a dynamic framework for heritage education, museum outreach, and public engagement, transforming prehistoric objects from passive artefacts into active narratives about human ingenuity and cultural identity.

Keywords: Hamangia; pointed tools; experimental.

Topic: New Technologies & Methods

**INTEGRATING PHOTOGRAMMETRY, 3D MODELING, AND THE
LATEST AI MODELS FOR HERITAGE PRESERVATION AND PUBLIC
DISSEMINATION: DIGITAL TWIN OF THE RELIQUARY OF ST.
MAURUS AS A PRIMARY CASE STUDY**

MATĚJ ŠINDELÁŘ¹

Abstract. The rapid advancement of digital technologies offers unprecedented opportunities for the non-destructive documentation and sustainable conservation of cultural heritage. This paper presents a comprehensive methodological workflow for the non-destructive digitization of archaeological findings (transforming them from entirely destructive to semi-destructive processes using modern technologies) and national treasures, utilizing the Reliquary of St. Maurus—a project set to represent the Czech Republic in the Europeana platform—as a primary case study. By employing high-resolution photography, advanced photogrammetry, and state-of-the-art 3D calculation software (including Reality Capture, the new RealityScan, MeshLab, and Blender), highly accurate digital twins are generated. The raw data is meticulously optimized to serve multidisciplinary teams comprising restorers, goldsmiths, gemologists, and art historians.

In close collaboration with expert restorer Andrej Šumbera, the project goes beyond static 3D modeling by digitally reconstructing 12th-century goldsmithing techniques, such as enameling, chasing, and repoussé. Furthermore, the project bridges the gap between expert conservation and socio-economic value by developing an interactive web-based application. This virtual museum experience allows the general public to explore intricate, micro-level details of the reliquary and other prominent artifacts (e.g., the Crown Jewels, the Cross of Závěš) without risking the physical integrity of the originals. The presentation will demonstrate how the fusion of modern 3D technology, artificial intelligence, and traditional restoration knowledge establishes a new paradigm for both the preservation of cultural legacy and its sustainable public presentation.

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Keywords: Digital heritage; photogrammetry; 3D Modeling; reliquary of St. Maurus; Europeana; virtual museum; non-destructive conservation; semi-destructive archaeological research.

Topic: New Technologies & Methods

THE "SKIN OF TIME": MEMORY, BEAUTY AND SAFETY OF HISTORIC BUILDINGS (DIAGNOSTICS AND RESTORATION)

GRAZIELLA ROSELLI¹

Abstract. The issue of the color of predominantly historic architecture or historic centers and their preservation is particularly difficult to address due to the many aspects involved in the issue. Complexity does not allow us to adopt precise guidelines to be applied in every circumstance, and for this reason, we can consider this issue still open and subject to continuous discussion between the different parties. We believe that this is a conservation issue whose importance is particularly relevant, especially in areas where disasters, especially earthquakes, lead us to intervene in the entire built-up area, not only in historic centers, with important and often very impactful interventions both from an urban and environmental point of view. We also believe that particular attention should be paid to the quality of historic mortars, a source of valuable information on the transformations undergone by valuable historic buildings, but also fundamental for a census of their quality, often closely linked to their vulnerability.

Keywords: Ancient building; plaster; colorimetry; mortars characterization.

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Topic: New Technologies & Methods

ARCHAEOLOGICAL INVESTIGATIONS ON EARLY NEOLITHIC POTTERY FROM SW ROMANIA

ADINA BORONEANȚ¹

Abstract. Pottery is the most abundant archaeological find at most sites, and yet, generally, we still know very little about it. Here, we go beyond the typological traditional approach limited to seriation and vessel shapes and attempt to learn more about pottery using computed tomography, LIBS, and electronic microscopy to respond to questions such as: how was it made, what does it consist of, how was it decorated, and where do the raw materials and coloring pigments come from.

Keywords: Early Neolithic; pottery; archaeometry.

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Topic: New Technologies & Methods

"LA POLICIORI" ROCK SHELTER AS A CASE STUDY FOR MODERN ROCK ART RECORDING METHODS

TOMA-ANDREI BUCUROIU^{1,2}

Abstract. The "La Policiori" rock shelter is part of the wider rupestrian phenomenon of the Nucu-Bozioru area in Buzău County, Romania. This was a hotspot for hermitage starting with the 14th century, mainly due to the complicated political and military context of wars with the major empires of the area, especially the Ottomans. The monks and hermits who fled to this area started excavating small rooms and chapels in the soft rock, creating the rock-hewn vestiges we see today, complete with dedicatory and votive inscriptions. One such vestige is "La Policiori", located in Ruginoasa village, marking the eastern-most point of the hermitage area. It is a small rock shelter, enlarged by hand, that has its floor covered with various signs, starting from the 15th century and up to a couple of years ago. This testifies to the local importance and continuation of use, but it finds itself in an advancing state of degradation. This is caused by both natural processes and the continuous visits by individuals who scratch or engrave their names next to the medieval signs. There are, however, alternatives. Modern recording techniques now allow us not only to better understand the distribution of the figures and their chronology, but also render possible the salvation of such delicate monuments by creating 3d models and digital tracings which can be placed on site and in museums.

Keywords: Rock art; medieval; digital recording methods.

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Topic: New Technologies & Methods

**ELLIPSOMETRY, TRANSMISSION, AND PHOTOLUMINESCENCE
CHARACTERIZATION OF MN-DOPED ITO THIN FILMS DEPOSITED
BY DC MAGNETRON SPUTTERING**

COSTEL CONSTANTIN¹

Abstract. Manganese-doped indium tin oxide (ITO) thin films (0–12.8 at% Mn) were deposited by DC magnetron sputtering. The structural, electrical, and optical properties of the films were studied. Optical characterization was emphasized and included measurements of ellipsometry, transmission, and photoluminescence (PL). Features of the energy band structure of ITO and Mn-ITO were extracted from PL spectra and TAUC analyses of absorption data. We concluded that the fundamental bandgap of ITO is ~2.8 eV. A separate deep valence band, ~0.8 eV below the valence band maximum, was confirmed to be involved in higher energy optical absorption and emission transitions. Both observations were consistent with recent theoretical studies and spectroscopic measurements (XPS, XES, etc.). Mn addition was found to decrease the transition energies. Additionally, Burstein–Moss shifts were observed.

Keywords: ITO; thin film; spectroscopic measurement.

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Topic: New Technologies & Methods

MAKING THE INVISIBLE VISIBLE: VISUALIZING MAGNETOMETRY DATA TO ALIGN STAKEHOLDER PRIORITIES IN HERITAGE CONSERVATION

ANDREEA POPA¹

Abstract. The preservation of subsurface cultural heritage faces a unique and persistent challenge: it is entirely out of sight and, consequently, often excluded from priority-balancing discussions during land development or budget allocations. While geophysical methods like magnetometry are highly effective at mapping unexcavated sites, raw magnetic data and complex greyscale plots are often inaccessible to non-expert decision-makers. This paper explores the critical role of visual communication in translating complex magnetometry results into actionable, persuasive conservation strategies. Within the framework of Importance-Performance Analysis (IPA), establishing the "Importance" of a buried site is the first required step before stakeholders will commit to the "Performance" of protecting it—whether through legal designation, route alteration in infrastructure projects, or funding allocation. This presentation demonstrates how processing and interpreting magnetometric data into clear, accessible visual narratives bridges the gap between archaeological science and heritage policy. By utilizing advanced visualization techniques—such as color-coded interpretation maps, 3D terrain overlays, and simplified structural models—archaeologists can clearly articulate the spatial extent, density, and historical significance of a site without moving a single trowel of earth. Ultimately, the paper argues that the strategic visualization of non-destructive survey data is not just a scientific output, but a vital advocacy tool. It empowers heritage professionals to actively engage urban planners, investors, and local communities, ensuring that the invisible archaeological record is accurately weighed and prioritized in modern heritage management.

Keywords: heritage; magnetometry; persuasive conservation strategy.

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Topic: Heritage between Past and Future

BETWEEN LOSS AND CONTINUITY: COLLECTIVE MEMORY AND HERITAGE LANDSCAPES IN THE NETHERLANDS

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Abstract. This article examines the dual dimensions of Dutch heritage landscapes: those that have been lost to urbanization yet survive in collective memory and those that are physically preserved but often culturally disconnected. We distinguish two categories – “Lost Landscapes” (erasures of former natural or rural terrain now overbuilt) and “Preserved Landscapes” (intact polders, dunes, fields, orchards, heaths, and forests) – and analyze how each is imbued with meaning and how communities can re-engage with them. Drawing on collective memory theory (Halbwachs), landscape historiography (Schama, Stewart & Strathern), and heritage planning frameworks (Kalman; Oevermann et al.), we argue that landscapes function as embodied archives of social memory. Lost Landscapes – such as drained marshes and demolished villages – remain vivid in art (e.g., Dutch Golden Age paintings) and oral history, and can be reanimated through sensory and participatory means. Preserved Landscapes – including national parks, polders, and agricultural regions – often suffer fragmentation by infrastructure and social change, yet inclusive mobility, multisensory design, and cultural programming can reconnect them to collective identity. We synthesize case studies (historic polder design, community archives, and heritage routes) and propose integrative interventions. Our findings indicate that mobilizing memory, art, and community in tandem is crucial to safeguard these landscape legacies for the future.

Keywords: Collective memory; cultural heritage; housing; energy transition; preserved/lost landscape; dune landscape; memory of dunes; cultural elements.

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Topic: Heritage between Past and Future

CONSERVATION ETHICS AND SACRED HERITAGE: REFLECTIONS FROM A MEGILLAT ESTHER

LUÍS FILIPE RAPOSO PEREIRA¹

Abstract. A treatment of a Megillat Esther (Scroll of Esther) undertaken at the Polytechnic Institute of Tomar has served as a point of departure for a broader, two-year reflection on the ethical and methodological challenges involved in conserving Jewish sacred objects. Beyond the technical intervention itself, the study carried out over this period has explored the complex interplay between halakhic prescriptions, ritual function, and professional conservation ethics. As a result, it has underscored the scarcity of clear, accessible guidelines and scholarly research addressing the care of ritual heritage, leaving conservators with limited reference frameworks when dealing with objects of living religious significance. Drawing on contemporary approaches to values-based and community-centred conservation, it is argued that interdisciplinary collaboration should be established between conservators, Jewish scholars, and religious authorities in order to develop coherent, context-sensitive ethical protocols that respect both the material integrity and the spiritual meaning of sacred artefacts.

Keywords: Conservation ethics; sacred objects; Jewish heritage; religious heritage preservation; intercultural conservation practices; parchment conservation.

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Topic: Heritage between Past and Future

RETHINKING CONSERVATION TRAINING THROUGH ETHNOGRAPHIC COLLECTIONS

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Abstract. This paper presents the development and implementation of the course Conservation of Ethnographic Collections at the Polytechnic Institute of Tomar, first introduced in 2024 as part of a revised undergraduate curriculum in Conservation and Restoration. The course has provided an opportunity to introduce new approaches to conservation training by engaging students with a wide range of object typologies while foregrounding their social contexts, cultural meanings, and intangible values. The teaching methodologies adopted will be presented. These combine theoretical instruction with practice-based and reflective learning strategies. The paper will also discuss the outcomes observed since the course's implementation, including student engagement, critical thinking development, and the ability to address complex conservation challenges. A critical assessment of the course will be offered, reflecting on its potential as an innovative model for conservation education that moves beyond object-centred approaches towards more inclusive and context-aware practices.

Keywords: Conservation education; ethnographic collections; cultural significance; community engagement; autoethnography.

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Topic: Heritage between Past and Future

IONIZING RADIATION RISK IN CULTURAL HERITAGE CONSERVATION ACTIVITIES

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Abstract. This paper investigates the occupational and public health risks associated with ionizing radiation within the field of cultural heritage conservation: radon exposure during and after structural restoration and direct exposure from curated collections. During the restoration of historic buildings, particularly those with underground floors, poor ventilation, or specific geological formations in the soil, radon gas accumulation poses a significant risk. We analyze how remediation of historic buildings for energy efficiency and climate control can inadvertently increase radon exposure for onsite conservators and visitors as members of the public. In addition, the paper examines the potential radioactivity present in objects displayed in museums. The case studies include: military technology (radium-226 dials and luminous instrumentation), natural history collections (high Uranium-238 activity concentrations found in fossilized remains), and decorative arts (ceramic glazes and pigments such as "uranium orange" used in 19th and 20th-century aesthetics). Evaluation of these risks is essential in ensuring the longevity of heritage buildings and artifacts, without compromising the health of the conservator or the visiting public.

Keywords: Radon; NORM; natural radioactivity.

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Topic: Heritage between Past and Future

EVOLUTION OF MORPHOLOGICAL ANALYSIS OF WROCŁAW QUARTER DEVELOPMENT IN THE AREA OF FORMER SAND GATE AND ITS IMPACT ON MODERN URBAN STRUCTURE

JUSTYNA KLESZCZ¹

Abstract. This presentation addresses the challenge of conducting a comprehensive analysis of the transformation process in the development of urban blocks in inner-city neighborhoods, using Wrocław as a case study – a city with a rich tradition and multicultural history, whose fortunes mirror the turbulent history of many European cities. The research aimed to illustrate the transformations of the built environment in the Old Town area from the appearance of the first forms of development in the analyzed area, through the establishment of the charter city, to the present day. The analysis was conducted using the example of a Wrocław quarter situated within the original charter city and bounded by Ducha Świętego, Kraińskiego and Jana Ewangelisty Purkyniego Streets, Nowy Targ Square, and Piaskowa Street – an area of historical significance for the city due to its location directly adjacent to the city walls on the side facing Ostrów Tumski. The study shows the changing form and structure of the urban block itself – an urban unit constituting the city in its most original form, which was, however, characterized by significant boundary shifts due to the radical changes occurring in the city's structure, from the foundation of the city through the incorporation of new territories and alterations to the defensive system, right through to the emergence of new urban functions, which was reflected in the morphology of the built environment in this area. The analysis concludes with a presentation of the most recent changes in this area, in connection with efforts to rebuild and consolidate the city's structure following the destruction of the Second World War. This analysis highlights the complexity of the evolutionary process shaping the built environment at the very center of a large city. Although this evolution and the series of changes in how the urban block takes shape differ in each instance, certain stages and turning points recur more frequently. A comparison with the structure of other urban blocks confirms

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the presence of several fundamental elements that jointly determine the development of the urban block. These are: the formal establishment of Nowy Targ around 1263; the construction of town fortifications; the demolition of the town fortifications from 1807 onwards; and war damage culminating in the final demolition of a significant part of the surviving buildings, followed by the decision on the contemporary development of the quarter.

The presented chronology of changes in the morphological structure reveals a process of urban fabric transformation that differs from the principles governing the shaping of a typical inner-city quarter. Until the early 19th century, development proceeded linearly rather than radially, creating increasingly dense layouts: formalized along the western frontage, with greater freedom towards the east (towards the barrier to development). The formalization of the building layout necessitated the development of compact frontage development in this area, though initially only along a single street, the course of which was determined by the pre-settlement trade route. The emergence of a second, secondary frontage on the southern side is clearly visible in the pattern of land parceling. It is linked to the settlement's location outside the original city boundary, as the so-called New Town on the eastern side. The current structure of the urban block represents a vague compromise between the decision to recreate the historical (albeit simplified) layout of neighboring areas and the modernist ideal of openness, alongside a 21st-century attempt to create a contemporary form grounded in historical experience.

Keywords: Wrocław quarter; parcellation; urban planning; Sand Gate; market hall.

Topic: Heritage between Past and Future

THE ROLE OF CULTURAL HERITAGE IN POST-EARTHQUAKE RESILIENCE: THE CHURCH OF SAN FRANCESCO IN CAMERINO

BEATRICE MENGHINI¹

Abstract. The core of the study centers on the Church of San Francesco in Camerino. Despite its current inaccessibility, a combination of indirect analysis and historical documentation has allowed for a preliminary reconstruction of its original 13th-century layout and subsequent 14th- and 15th-century interventions. Key findings include the identification of a dismantled funerary monument—likely the original tomb of Blessed Giovanni da Parma—characterized by a Gothic canopy structure. Furthermore, architectural indicators and 18th-century descriptions provide evidence for the existence of a monumental tramezzo (rood screen) and a specific choir arrangement. By digitally "repositioning" detached frescoes and lost architectural elements, this work demonstrates how virtual tools serve not merely as visual aids but as essential instruments for scientific research and the restoration of cultural context to communities deprived of their physical heritage.

Keywords: Franciscan architecture; virtual reconstruction; San Francesco in Camerino; Central-Italy 2016 earthquake.

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Topic: Heritage between Past and Future

UNVEILING THE WALL PAINTING TECHNIQUE FROM THE GOVERNOR'S PALACE IN APULUM. PRELIMINARY REMARKS

DUMITRIȚA DANIELA FILIP¹, VIORICA RUSU-BOLINDEȚ², GHEORGHINA OLARIU³

Abstract. This study is part of a larger research project aiming, on the one hand, at reconstructing the wall painting techniques from Apulum and identifying and characterizing the materials used. On the other hand, the project aims at developing a restoration methodology adapted to the specificity of the wall-painted fragments discovered in several archaeological excavations located on different sites that belonged to the ancient city. Among these, the Governor's Palace is one of the most important settlements in Apulum and Roman Dacia, the headquarters of the Governor of the Three Dacias. This paper aims to gain insights into the technique and the materials utilized by the Roman painters/craftsmen to decorate the walls of the palace. Thus, 15 wall-painted fragments discovered during the systematic archaeological excavations were scientifically investigated. Preliminary results of the physical-chemical investigations using optical microscopy and XRF will be presented here. For the future, the data will be completed by other ongoing minimally invasive methods in order to obtain more detailed information.

Keywords: Roman wall painting; pigments; Apulum; OM; XRF.

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Topic: Heritage between Past and Future

CHARACTERIZATION AND CONSERVATION OF A GRAPHIC DESIGN COLLECTION: CASE STUDY COLLECTION B2, SALETTE AND JOSÉ BRANDÃO DESIGN STUDIO

MARIA CATANHEIRA PEREIRA DE MOURA BELO¹

Abstract. This topic addresses the particularities of characterizing and conserving a graphic design collection, starting from a case study: the incorporation of the B2 collection, José Brandão and Sallette Brandão, into the MUDE – Museum of Design, in Lisbon. We understand that, as in the universe of contemporary art, a graphic design collection presents distinct challenges compared to ancient art. Whether in identifying its materiality, temporality, or destination, dealing with a graphic design collection goes beyond the relationship with the singular piece or the result of a project; the collection involves the management of mass-produced pieces (such as posters or pamphlets) but also unique documents that illustrate the design process itself. A graphic design collection is usually made up of a volume of materials that, potentially disposable in the context of production (in the private environment of a studio), gain museographic potential when they are patrimonialized and communicated, allowing reflection and debate on the concept of collection, archive, and design work. MUDE establishes its own language for characterizing the collection and benefits from direct contact with designers and artists for the integration of pieces. Always starting from conservation as an ethical and philosophical exercise, and not just a material one, for decision-making, MUDE presents strategies and procedures to adapt to the reality of Design, constantly adapting to encounter new pieces and realities.

Keywords: Graphic design; conservation; MUDE; B2; José Brandão.

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Topic: Heritage between Past and Future

BRIDGING PAST AND FUTURE: A STUDY OF NUCLEAR HERITAGE IN ROMANIA

CLAUDIA STIHI¹

Abstract. Nuclear heritage is a distinct aspect of heritage that links historical nuclear practices and scientific knowledge to current applications and future developments. In Romania, nuclear heritage can be recognized as a significant component of the country's scientific and cultural heritage, as a bridge between past achievements and the emerging trajectory of the nuclear field. Romania's historical achievements in the nuclear field are linked to future-oriented applications, including nuclear power plants, research reactors, and specialized technological infrastructure. Key challenges, such as radiation protection and nuclear waste management, intersect with the application of nuclear techniques for the analysis and conservation of cultural heritage objects. The paper presents key elements of Romania's nuclear heritage and demonstrates the importance of understanding and their valorization.

Keywords: Past; future; bridge; nuclear; heritage.

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Topic: Heritage between Past and Future

CULTURAL HERITAGE AT RISK: PRESERVATION OF ARCHITECTURE IN CONFLICT ZONES

SVITLANA LINDA¹

Abstract. The paper is devoted to the pressing issues of preserving architectural heritage in the context of armed conflicts. It examines the main threats faced by architectural monuments, ranging from physical destruction to the loss of cultural identity, and analyzes international approaches to their protection and restoration. Particular attention is paid to the situation in Ukraine, where, as a result of the war, a significant number of historical buildings and cultural sites have been threatened with destruction or have already suffered damage. The paper emphasizes the importance of consolidating efforts by the state, international organizations, and society to preserve cultural heritage as an integral part of national memory and global culture.

Keywords: Cultural heritage; architectural preservation; armed conflict; war damage; historical monuments; Ukraine; cultural protection; restoration; heritage conservation.

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Topic: Heritage between Past and Future

HERITAGE FUTURES IN EASTERN EUROPE: REWILDING AND SELECTIVE CONSERVATION IN POST-SOCIALIST LANDSCAPES

LUCIA NOVÁKOVÁ¹, SILVIU MILOIU²

Abstract. Across post-socialist Eastern Europe, deindustrialization and infrastructural transformation have produced extensive landscapes of abandonment: disused railway corridors, industrial complexes, unfinished hydraulic projects, military sites, and closed mines. In countries such as Romania and Slovakia, the volume of these material remains far exceeds the capacity of conventional heritage protection. At the same time, many such sites are being reshaped by spontaneous ecological succession or planned regeneration, generating new ecologies and new forms of public use. This paper asks under what conditions rewilding and curated decay can be understood as legitimate forms of selective conservation rather than neglect. It also considers how decisions to retain, transform, or deliberately relinquish material remains can be justified in ways that are historically grounded, transparent, and ethically defensible. The discussion draws on heritage futures approaches, which understand conservation not simply as the preservation of the past, but as a practice of shaping possible futures under conditions of uncertainty and surplus.

Keywords: Rewilding; curated decay; conservation; Slovakia; Romania.

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Topic: Heritage between Past and Future

FROM GRAVE GOODS TO GALLERY NARRATIVES: WOMEN'S AGENCY IN THE CHRISTIANISATION OF SWEDEN AND NORWAY

SILVIU MILOIU¹, ELENA-ADRIANA CIOCOIU¹, IOAN ALEXANDRU VĂLU¹

Abstract. Archaeological discoveries from Sweden and Norway have long shaped scholarly and public understandings of the Christianisation of Scandinavia, a process traditionally interpreted through a predominantly masculine lens centered on kings, warriors, and elite male actors. This paper re-examines key archaeological findings from the Viking Age and early medieval period, particularly graves, personal objects, and ritual assemblages, through the prism of women's agency, highlighting how material culture associated with women played a crucial role in the transmission, adaptation, and domestication of Christian beliefs. The study adopts a diachronic approach to heritage interpretation, tracing three interrelated stages: the initial discovery and documentation of archaeological material; the evolution of scholarly interpretations regarding women's religious and social roles; and the subsequent mediation of these interpretations in museum displays and public history. Special attention is paid to how early scholarship marginalized or neutralized gendered evidence, reinforcing narratives of top-down Christianisation led by male authority, and how more recent interdisciplinary research—drawing on archaeology, gender studies, and religious history—has progressively recontextualized women as active cultural and religious agents. By analyzing exhibition strategies and curatorial practices in selected Swedish and Norwegian museums, the paper demonstrates how revised academic interpretations have begun to reshape public perceptions of Norse Christianisation, challenging heroic and exclusively masculine imaginaries. These shifts illustrate the dynamic relationship between past and future in cultural heritage: archaeological material remains constant, yet its meanings evolve as methodological frameworks and societal values change. Ultimately, the paper argues that foregrounding women's agency in Christianisation narratives not only enhances historical accuracy but also exemplifies the importance of reflexive, inclusive heritage conservation. In doing so, it contributes to broader debates

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on how reinterpretation, rather than preservation alone, can serve as a creative and socially responsive strategy for sustainable cultural heritage stewardship.

Keywords: Christianisation of Scandinavia; women's agency; archaeological interpretation; museum narratives; cultural heritage and memory; gender and Norse studies.

Topic: Heritage between Past and Future

**NEW MUSEOTECHNICAL METHODS APPLIED TO A CACHE OF
METAL ARTIFACTS FROM THE ARCHAEOLOGICAL COLLECTION
OF THE NATIONAL MUSEUM COMPLEX “CURTEA DOMNEASCĂ”,
TÂRGOVIȘTE (ROMANIA)**

ANA ILIE¹, ANDREI SCĂRLĂTESCU¹, TUDOR HILA¹, BOGDAN CIUPERCĂ¹

Abstract. The advancement of new digital technologies and the growth of globalization require the promotion of imagination and the capacity to innovate, including in the field of museum activities, particularly exhibitions, which are traditionally linked to exhibition halls and physical objects. To these general developments—shaping an audience accustomed to high consumption of dynamic, interactive, and collaborative social media—is added the chronic issue of underfunding of museums in Romania, which make difficult to implement large exhibitions in their traditional physical expression. General and specific trends have led us to focus on organizing a micro-exhibition by using new technical possibilities through digital interpretative means such as video reconstructions and digital models of artifacts. The showcased heritage is the result of an archaeological discovery: a hoard consisting of 42 metal objects. Most of these artifacts are made of iron, while the rest are made of copper or alloys. They are flat pieces, and from a conservation perspective, difficult to stabilize them, even though they have undergone a restoration process. These artifacts were the subject of a multimedia contextual interpretation, the result of collaboration between related disciplines, involving archaeologists, artists, and museographers specialized in 3D scans, the goals being to allow public access to archaeological and historical information both in mixed physical-digital format, exclusively in digital format, and subsequently to archive the digital form of them.

Keywords: Exhibition project; archaeology; metal artifacts; 3D scanning; virtual animations.

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Topic: Heritage between Past and Future

REDISCOVERING THE TATARS' MEDIEVAL HERITAGE ON THE TERRITORY OF THE REPUBLIC OF MOLDOVA

SERGIU MUSTEATA¹

Abstract. This paper addresses the rediscovery and reassessment of the medieval Tatar heritage on the present-day territory of the Republic of Moldova, situating it within contemporary debates on heritage between past and future. As part of the wider sphere of influence of the Golden Horde (13th–15th centuries), this region preserves a range of archaeological sites and cultural traces that remain insufficiently studied and largely absent from public narratives. Drawing on recent archaeological investigations, relevant historical sources, and spatial analysis, this study re-examines a series of sites associated with the Tatar presence, with particular attention to settlement configurations, communication networks, and material culture. It further addresses how historiographical traditions, the configuration of modern state borders, and evolving identity discourses have shaped the marginalization and, at times, the selective interpretation of this heritage. Framed within the conference theme, the paper argues that rediscovering Tatar heritage is not only an academic exercise but also a forward-looking cultural act. By integrating this layer of the medieval past into contemporary heritage frameworks, it becomes possible to promote more inclusive narratives, strengthen cross-border perspectives, and support sustainable heritage management strategies. Ultimately, the contribution highlights the potential of this rediscovered heritage to bridge past and future—transforming a neglected historical legacy into a resource for dialogue, identity, and cultural resilience in Eastern Europe.

Keywords: Tatars; Golden Hoard; Medieval Heritage; Republic of Moldova.

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Topic: Heritage between Past and Future

ETHICS AND EXPERTISE FOR THE BENEFIT OF CULTURAL HERITAGE

ANDREA BERNATH¹

Abstract. This contribution examines the essential relationship between ethics and professional expertise in the protection, preservation, and sustainable use of cultural heritage. It traces the origins of ethical considerations in the field of heritage protection and reflects on the development of the first Code of Ethics established by the International Council of Museums - ICOM. In light of contemporary changes, the 2004 Code of Ethics, while still valuable, no longer fully reflects current challenges, prompting an ongoing revision process, now in its fourth draft and shaped by broad consultation within the International Council of Museums community. The revised framework is built on five core principles - Society, Professionalism, Education, Collections, and Governance, which directly guide everyday museum practices, from community engagement to collection management and institutional decision-making. Through a range of practical examples, this contribution argues that responsible decision-making, grounded in ethical principles and supported by specialized expertise, is essential for ensuring that cultural assets are properly understood, researched, conserved, restored, and transmitted to future generations. Conversely, actions taken outside an informed, responsible, and up-to-date professional framework may lead to unintended consequences, ultimately placing cultural heritage at risk of damage or misinterpretation.

Keywords: Ethics; museum practices; cultural heritage.

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Topic: Heritage between Past and Future

**THE ICON PANEL IN WALLACHIA DURING THE 18TH–19TH
CENTURIES: HISTORICAL CONTEXT AND ASPECTS CONCERNING
THE MORPHOLOGY OF DEGRADATION, WITH PARTICULAR
EMPHASIS ON LIGHT AS A DETERIORATION FACTOR**

MARIA- CATALINA GHINEA^{1,2}

Abstract. The present study constitutes an interdisciplinary investigation into the study of the icon, focusing on its evolution during the 18th–19th centuries, the significance and patrimonial value of religious artifacts, and the establishment of an applied conservation-restoration methodology. Contemporary conservation-restoration methods are grounded in interdisciplinarity and involve the integration of historical and ethnological documentation with physicochemical and biological analyses, alongside the practical processes of conservation and restoration.

The paper examines the historical and ethnological context of the icon's evolution throughout the 18th–19th centuries, as well as the restoration methodology applied to a specific icon. Romanian iconography developed upon the foundations of Byzantine iconography, yet distinguishes itself from its model through the expressiveness of facial features and chromatic richness. Efremov, in *Romanian Icons*, observed that, in contrast to Greek or Russian icons—which tend to be either hermetic or abstract—Romanian icons display a facial expressiveness that is closer to the human condition. From a research perspective, the hypothesis that light—considered a fundamental factor in the degradation of pictorial images—is refuted through laboratory testing (comparative colorimetric analysis) conducted on both artificially aged and non-degraded samples. Following accelerated aging, the luminosity of the samples increases; however, as the number of pictorial layers rises, this ratio decreases. It can be observed that the total color difference between untreated and artificially degraded samples becomes negligible when more than six painted layers are present. The pigment applied to the preparation

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layer migrates into the ground layer, such that diffuse reflection involves a greater number of white calcium sulfate particles compared to reflection on a saturated surface. As the number of applied layers increases, the diffusion phenomenon reaches saturation, and reflectance measurements capture the contribution of the pigment layers primarily.

The study demonstrates, through physicochemical analyses and case studies, that light is not, in itself, a degrading factor for works of art. This hypothesis was tested and refuted in specialized laboratories through long-term, repetitive experiments. In order to identify observable changes in colorimetric parameters, artificial aging treatments were applied to experimental samples using a climate chamber (Binder APT Line KBF-ICH). By correlating the measurement results, it was concluded that mineral pigments do not degrade under the action of electromagnetic radiation in the visible and ultraviolet spectrum; the observed chromatic alterations are instead attributable to other factors related to the painting support and binding media.

Keywords: Icon; interdisciplinary; evolution throughout the 18th–19th centuries; light; colorimetric parameters.

Conference Track: Heritage between Past and Future

CULTURAL HERITAGE IN THE CONTEXT OF THE SMART SHRINKING CITIES: BETWEEN PAST AND FUTURE

ELITSA LAZAROVA¹

Abstract. There is a global trend toward shrinking cities, which leads to many challenges across social, economic, and cultural dimensions. The future city should be smart, face challenges (such as rethinking, repurposing, and reorganizing its infrastructure), and be more citizen-oriented. Conservation of cultural heritage is crucial to enhancing the city's identity, engaging citizens, fostering more active communities, improving residents' quality of life, and attracting new inhabitants. The paper maps the Bulgarian shrinking cities and examines the role of cultural heritage in the concept of the 15-minute city.

Keywords: Cultural heritage; smart shrinking cities; future city; 15-minute city.

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Topic: Heritage between Past and Future

**THE LIMITS OF PRIVATE INTERVENTION IN PUBLIC HERITAGE: A
MANAGERIAL CRITIQUE OF THE RADU VARIA RESTORATION
PROJECT ON BRÂNCUȘI'S ENDLESS COLUMN (1996–2000)**

MARIA STAMATE¹

Abstract. This paper provides a critical managerial analysis of the failed restoration project led by Radu Varia and the International Brâncuși Foundation regarding the Endless Column, the centerpiece of Constantin Brâncuși's monumental ensemble in Târgu Jiu. The study examines the period between 1996 and 2000, identifying the structural and ethical risks that emerge when public heritage of universal value is subjected to unilateral private oversight without rigorous state accountability. The research argues that the 1996 intervention—characterized by the illegal and unscientific dismantling of the Column—was a catastrophic failure in stakeholder management. By prioritizing personal prestige over established conservation protocols, the project utilized inadequate industrial methods that caused significant physical damage to the monument's cast-iron modules and central spine. The paper scrutinizes the administrative vacuum that allowed a private entity to bypass multidisciplinary expert consensus and international guidelines. The study concludes by contrasting this period of crisis with the subsequent scientifically-led restoration in 2000. It presents the 'Varia Case' as a definitive example of the dangers of personalizing heritage management, emphasizing that the preservation of Brâncuși's legacy requires a transparent, institutionalized framework that safeguards public interest against the arbitrary nature of private ambition.

Keywords: Brâncuși; Endless Column; Varia; Târgu Jiu; Heritage; UNESCO; World Heritage; Restoration.

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Topic: Heritage between Past and Future

**COST-EFFICIENCY IN SUBSURFACE HERITAGE MANAGEMENT:
AN IMPORTANCE-PERFORMANCE ANALYSIS OF
MAGNETOMETRY AT THE RECI-COMOLĂU CIVILIAN
SETTLEMENT IN SE TRANSYLVANIA**

ALEXANDRU POPA¹

Abstract. Cultural heritage conservation frequently operates under strict financial and temporal constraints, requiring heritage managers to balance priorities between modern development and preservation. This paper evaluates the application of magnetic prospection through the lens of Importance-Performance Analysis (IPA), utilizing the civilian settlement of the Roman fortification at Reci-Comolău—a component of the UNESCO World Heritage Site "Frontiers of the Roman Empire"—as a primary case study. During the initial phase of a regional development project, the structure proposed by the beneficiary and the designer partially overlapped with the Roman civilian settlement due to land availability constraints. Given the site's prestigious UNESCO status, an extensive magnetometric survey of the area was implemented to evaluate the archaeological "Importance" and establish precise spatial boundaries prior to any ground disturbance. The results provided a high-resolution map of the subsurface structures, demonstrating that modifying the project's design parameters could completely avoid intrusion into the site, limiting construction exclusively to its legal protection zone.

From the perspective of "**Performance**," this non-invasive approach generated substantial savings in both time and financial resources that would otherwise have been consumed by highly complex and expensive preventive rescue excavations. The paper demonstrates how these conserved resources can be strategically redirected toward partnerships between the responsible museum and the local municipality.

Consequently, rather than expending budgets on archaeological discharge, funds can be invested in site landscaping and improving public accessibility.

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Ultimately, magnetometry has proven an essential tool for proactive heritage management, optimizing budgets, mitigating stakeholder conflicts, and maximizing the social impact of conservation efforts at sites of outstanding universal value.

Keywords: Heritage; UNESCO site; magnetoscopic survey.

Topic: Traditional & Innovative Materials

ADVANCED CHARACTERIZATION OF SUBSTRATE MATERIALS USED IN MURAL PAINTING IN THE A SECCO TECHNIQUE – CASE STUDY: THE ROYAL RAILWAY STATION OF CURTEA DE ARGÈȘ

MARIUS LUNGESCU¹, MARIA-CATALINA GHINEA²

Abstract. The a secco painting technique exhibits reduced durability over time compared to fresco; chromatic reintegration and varnishing interventions tend to lead, in a relatively short period, to extensive and progressive degradation phenomena. From the perspective of material composition, lime-based mortars with sand aggregates can be considered the most compatible with the original substrate, as they display similar physical and mechanical properties. The characterization of mortars involves both physical and mechanical parameters. Physically, this includes water absorption capacity, density, adhesion to the substrate layer, and permeability to atmospheric water vapor. Mechanically, reference is made to flexural strength and compressive strength. The variation in these strength parameters must remain minimal or, at most, moderate for the materials to be suitable for conservation-restoration interventions. The railway station building stands out through its elegance and sobriety, being constructed in a style that combines Neoclassical and Neo-Gothic influences, characteristic of late 19th-century public architecture. It is a symmetrical and imposing structure, single-storied, yet possessing a monumental appearance. At the time the restoration works commenced, the building was in an advanced state of degradation. Multiple inappropriate interventions, both exterior and interior, had rendered the original surface inaccessible. These conditions resulted from inadequate rehabilitation efforts, some involving the complete removal of original plaster layers, while others consisted of the application of successive paint layers onto the surface. Over time, these interventions led to active degradation processes, including swelling, exfoliation involving the original layer, extensive lacunae, and loss of original material. Consequently, a tailored

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intervention methodology was developed, specific to this case. Comprehensive photographic documentation was undertaken, both in direct and raking light. Areas were designated for stratigraphic surveys, alongside macroscopic and microscopic investigations, as well as spectrophotometric analyses carried out on both the original material and the intervention layers. All these measures aim to establish a conservation-restoration plan for the monument, in accordance with established restoration principles.

Keywords: Mortars; material composition; analyses; conservation-restoration plan.

Topic: Other

HERITAGE PUBLIC SPACES, EXCLUDED USERS: ACCESSIBILITY OF SMALL-TOWN MARKET SQUARES IN SOUTHERN POLAND

MARCIN GAŁKOWSKI¹

Abstract. The following presentation will outline the findings of a study conducted to assess the accessibility of heritage market squares in small towns in the Opole region of Poland (in the southern part of the country). The study was conducted using participatory assisted walks. The research focused on recently revitalised heritage spaces to determine whether the implemented changes improve accessibility for people with special needs. The results indicate that none of the urban spaces examined guarantee safe and independent utilization of the space for individuals with disabilities, with the circumstances for those with visual impairments being especially challenging. The primary impediments stem from the quality of the pavement and the organisation of traffic, namely the presence of uneven, variably surfaced roads, the absence of clearly marked pedestrian pathways and crossings, and the illogical arrangement of parking spaces. The study under scrutiny here highlights the scale of accessibility issues in small urban heritage centres in Poland and identifies directions for change in the design standards for open public spaces.

Keywords: Accessibility; public spaces; Europe; universal access; universal design.

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Conference Track: Other

BIODEGRADABLE PLASTICS IN CROP PRODUCTION: EFFECTS ON SOIL ENVIRONMENT AND AGRONOMIC PERFORMANCE

ZAMEER HUSSAIN JAMALI¹

Abstract. The increasing concern over environmental sustainability has intensified the need for eco-friendly alternatives to conventional agricultural practices that contribute to long-term ecosystem degradation. In modern crop production systems, the extensive use of polyethylene mulch films has raised significant environmental issues due to their persistence in soil and contribution to plastic pollution, which ultimately affects soil health and ecosystem functioning.

This study evaluates biodegradable plastic mulches as a sustainable solution that aligns with principles of environmental conservation and soil ecosystem protection. A multi-year field experiment will be conducted at the Faculty of Agriculture and Technology, University of South Bohemia in České Budějovice, Czech Republic, using soybean (*Glycine max* L.) as a model crop. The study compares biodegradable mulch films (PLA-, PBAT-based), conventional polyethylene mulch, straw mulch, and a non-mulched control under field conditions.

The research focuses on key indicators of environmental and agronomic sustainability, including soil physical, chemical, and biological properties, soil microclimate regulation, weed suppression efficiency, crop performance, and mulch degradation dynamics. Particular attention is given to how biodegradable materials interact with soil microbial communities and contribute to organic matter cycling, thereby supporting ecosystem resilience.

By integrating agricultural productivity with environmental conservation principles, this study contributes to the broader discussion on sustainable land management and the reduction of plastic pollution in agroecosystems. The findings are expected to support evidence-based strategies for balancing agricultural efficiency with long-term ecological sustainability, aligning with global priorities for sustainable development and environmental protection.

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Topic: Other

ELECTROTYPE OF THE PARADE SHIELD "CELLINI" FROM THE ROYAL COLLECTION OF PELEȘ CASTLE

RALUCA ROMOK¹

Abstract. The subject of my research is the electrotype of the parade shield universally known as the “Cellini shield”, reminiscent of Benvenuto Cellini (1500–1571), the Italian goldsmith and sculptor, and the famous representative of Italian Mannerism. I’ll start from the question: “What could be the connection between the Victoria & Albert Museum in London, the Metropolitan Museum in New York, the Peleș National Museum in Sinaia, Prince Albert, Queen Victoria’s husband, and King Charles III of Great Britain?” Well, this impressive shield is what connects the five elements—the shield from which the story began, and which is now located at Windsor Castle, in King Charles III’s Guard Room.

Keywords: Cellini shield; Queen Victoria and Prince Albert; Victoria & Albert Museum; Windsor; Peleș Castle.

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Topic: Other

FROM STUDENTS' VOICE TO CURRICULUM DESIGN IN APPLIED SCIENCES – BUILDING AN ECO-CULTURAL HERITAGE MASTER'S ALIGNED WITH THE GREEN AND DIGITAL TRANSITIONS

LAURA MONICA GORGHIU¹, GABRIEL GORGHIU², SILVIU MILOIU³

Abstract. While the application of science to eco-cultural heritage in Romanian education is a growing field, it currently lacks a general strategy and remains fragmented and niche-oriented. Nonetheless, the foundations of this interdisciplinary approach are discernible across both academic and pre-university levels. Major universities have begun introducing master's programs that combine heritage with technology and environmental studies, even though they are not labelled as "eco-cultural heritage" but are covered in several master's programs. Several digital projects are also implemented to transform heritage management digitally. At the pre-university level, under the umbrella of Sustainability Education and with the major opportunities offered by the "School in another way" and "Green week" programmes, a series of themes, or even projects, that link the environment and heritage are discussed and developed, involving museums or NGOs that manage historical sites.

This paper presents the perceived relevance of the proposed master's programme "Sciences in Eco-Cultural Heritage" to the needs, long-term aspirations and educational/professional trajectories of undergraduate students, postgraduate students and alumni of the Faculty of Sciences and Arts, Valahia University of Târgoviște (UVT). Following a survey, we examined three dimensions: career aspirations; expectations regarding skills and learning outcomes; and pedagogical preferences, including learning formats and assessment approaches. The findings have been translated into an operational curriculum that connects students' voices with international standards and

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quality assurance requirements, aligning it with the green and digital transition, and with heritage- and community-based practice. The design integrates GreenComp, the 2018 Key Competences for Lifelong Learning, ICOMOS reference frameworks, and UNESCO indicators, pursuing a dual objective: long-term employability and measurable socio-cultural impact. The proposed programme supports an interdisciplinary, highly skilled workforce capable of addressing climate-related risks, strengthening cultural resilience, and fostering sustainable human–environment relationships.

Keywords: Applied sciences; eco-cultural heritage; master curriculum; sustainable development; green and digital transitions.

Topic: Socio-Economic Value

CRAFT-ORIENTED EDUCATIONAL HERITAGE

KATARZYNA ŁUKANISZYN-DOMASZEWSKA¹, KATARZYNA MAZUR-
WŁODARCZYK¹

Abstract. *Research Background:* In the face of dynamic global changes and digitalization, traditional craftsmanship faces the challenge of maintaining cultural authenticity while ensuring economic viability. Educational heritage, encompassing both tangible and intangible assets, plays a pivotal role in this process, acting as a bridge between historical techniques and modern market demands.

Purpose: This article aims to identify and analyze the various forms of educational heritage in the craft sector and to evaluate the impact of innovative technologies and social capital on the development of small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) based on traditional skills.

Methodology: The study employs a systematic literature review and a comparative analysis of international research projects (e.g., Mingei, CRAEFT, Digitizing the Deep Past). Qualitative content analysis and thematic coding were used to categorize manifestations of educational heritage into family, institutional, and social dimensions.

Findings: The research reveals that the survival of modern crafts depends on a synergy between traditional apprenticeship models and advanced digital tools such as VR, AR, and AI. These technologies do not replace manual skills but rather enhance engagement and facilitate intergenerational knowledge transfer. Furthermore, the study identifies that "Living Human Treasures" programs and heritage tourism are essential for the sustainable development of the craft-based industry.

Practical Implications: The results provide a framework for craft chambers, museums, and educational institutions to develop more effective training programs. For SMEs, the study highlights the importance of the "cultural premium" and diversity as strategic resources in Value-Based Management and social capital building.

Value/Originality: This paper contributes to the field by proposing a holistic model of educational craft heritage (categorized into family, teaching, and social forms) and

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demonstrating how digital innovation can catalyze preserving intangible cultural heritage in the 21st-century economy.

Keywords: Cultural heritage; educational heritage; craft; regional development; cultural economics; intangible cultural heritage.

Topic: Socio-Economic Value

RETHINKING AND ACTIVATING HERITAGE AS A SOCIO-ECONOMIC RESOURCE IN DRAGU, ROMANIA

ALINA CHICIUDEAN¹

Abstract. The intervention carried out in 2025 in the village of Dragu (Sălaj County, Romania) aligns with a broader effort to redefine heritage practice through the concept of a “living laboratory.” More specifically, the intervention consisted of an international summer school, interdisciplinary field research, and a series of cultural activation events, ranging from guided tours and community workshops to open-access cultural gatherings, designed to simultaneously document, interpret, and reactivate the local heritage context. Within this framework, the cultural and natural landscape became the testing ground for a working hypothesis: that heritage can and should be understood not as a static asset, but as a layered system of built, natural, and intangible values. Initiated by ARCHÉ, the process was conceived as a process of co-production with the local community, where research, education, and cultural activation overlap and inform one another in real time.

This framework enabled simultaneous research, experimentation, and community interaction. The intention was not to apply a predefined model, but to explore whether a site-specific methodology could emerge organically from within the local context. In doing so, the initiative positioned itself deliberately outside conventional restoration timelines, which typically follow a linear sequence, from funding to documentation and technical assessment, design, and eventual intervention, often detached from immediate community engagement. Instead, the process at Dragu inverted this logic, prioritizing activation and collective use as catalysts for knowledge production and future intervention.

The initial encounter revealed a paradox common in many rural contexts: a community emotionally attached to a deteriorating monument yet structurally disconnected from the processes required to rehabilitate it. The Wesselényi-Bethlen Castle served as both an anchor and a pretext, enabling a broader inquiry into the village’s cultural landscape. What began as an initiative centered on a partially collapsed monument quickly

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expanded into a broader territorial mapping and evolved into a complex engagement with a multi-layered heritage environment. The discovery was not the existence of heritage itself, but its intensity within a remarkably limited spatial frame: built structures (traditional houses, the wooden church, the historic mill, the former aristocratic cellars), cultural memory, biodiversity, and landscape coexisting in a dense and interdependent system. This rural setting revealed a concentration of heritage values rarely encountered in practice, yet often described in theory.

This shift from object to system required a continuous recalibration of methods, priorities, and even expectations. A key finding of the project lies in the role of community agency. The local administration's long-term efforts, combined with a latent openness within the community, created the conditions for collaboration. Initial perceptions of heritage as a burden gradually evolved into an understanding of its fragile yet tangible economic and social potential. This transformation was neither linear nor externally driven: it emerged through dialogue, shared activities, and, at times, correction from the community itself. In this sense, the process also exposed the limits of top-down approaches. A series of critical key moments emerged as milestones to be negotiated and overcome, often arising from differences in scale, expectations, and language. Rather than obstructing progress, these tensions proved productive, leading to more well-anchored and realistic approaches.

Through an international summer school, interdisciplinary research, and a series of public events, the project mobilized both local knowledge and external expertise. Events such as "Danț în Șură," the "Fain de Dragu" festival, and participatory workshops functioned as mediating tools, translating specialist discourse into shared experience. At the same time, the entire process maintained a strong research component, including architectural documentation, material analysis, and digital recording. Cultural tourism emerged as a secondary outcome rather than a primary objective, while temporary events contributed to longer-term shifts in perception and engagement.

Rather than offering definitive solutions, the approach calls for a shift in perspective: heritage is not only a problem to be solved but a resource to be activated through an ongoing process of negotiation, in which tensions, constraints, and opportunities continuously generate both challenges and solutions. This reflection on the first year of intervention examines the interplay between expert knowledge and local agency. It evaluates the role of cultural events in opening new imaginaries, while simultaneously addressing the limits of the model's transferability. The Dragu experiment raises a critical question for future practice: can such locally embedded, adaptive models be sustained and replicated without losing their specificity? While the methodology may be transferable, its success remains contingent on specific social and institutional conditions. What distinguishes the Dragu case is not the mere confirmation of a widely established premise, that heritage can support community cohesion, but the way in

which a fragile, under-resourced context absorbed a disruptive, open-ended process and transformed it into a locally grounded trajectory of development. The intervention demonstrates that meaningful outcomes do not emerge despite friction, but through it. The findings point to the need to expand applied experiments in sustainable heritage practices in rural contexts, grounded in horizontal learning frameworks. In this field, nothing can (or should) be fully predefined: processes must remain adaptive, iterative, and deeply embedded in place. Ultimately, the Dragu case suggests that heritage, when approached as a shared resource rather than an isolated artifact, can foster both community cohesion and new economic perspectives.

Keywords: Living laboratory; ARCHE; heritage.

Topic: Socio-Economic Value

CULTURAL HERITAGE AS A RESOURCE FOR MENTAL HEALTH AND WELL-BEING

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Abstract. Cultural heritage plays an increasingly recognized role in supporting mental health and well-being, offering individuals and communities a sense of identity, continuity, and belonging. This paper explores the relationship between tangible and intangible cultural heritage and mental well-being, focusing on how engagement with heritage practices, sites, and narratives can foster emotional resilience, social connection, and psychological restoration. Drawing on interdisciplinary perspectives from management, economics, psychology, heritage studies, and public health, the study examines heritage as both a protective factor during crises and a therapeutic resource in everyday life. Particular attention is given to community-based heritage initiatives and participatory practices that empower marginalized groups and promote inclusive well-being. The paper argues that integrating heritage into mental health and well-being strategies can contribute to more holistic and culturally sensitive approaches to care and prevention, thereby building a resilient society.

Keywords: Cultural heritage; well-being; mental health; heritage management; social and economic resilience; cultural economics; cultural diversity.

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Balancing priorities: An importance-performance analysis of cultural heritage conservation

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Balancing priorities: An importance-performance analysis of cultural heritage conservation

Gender

■ Men ■ Women

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